

INNOVATION PROCUREMENT IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR

Comparative analysis with recent
PCP/PPI from other sectors
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INNOVATION PROCUREMENT IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR Comparative analysis with recent PCP/PPI from other sectors

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**LEA – LEARNING
TECHNOLOGY
ACCELERATOR**

[>WEBSITE<](#)

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1. INTRO

Since 2018, LEA project has been contributing to the knowledge transfer, dialogue and awareness-raising of innovation procurement within the learning technology sector.

Within LEA's strategy of enhancing stakeholders' knowledge and skills, this document aims at positioning the procurement for innovation in the education sector within the larger innovative procurement ecosystem. For doing that, we compare the first and only PCP project conducted within the education sector, at EU level — IMAILE — with other three PCP projects, gathering a summary of the main actions and best practices identified by them when conducting their own innovation procurement processes. Also, to empower stakeholders of knowledge concerning the next steps after a PCP project, we provide a summary of the actions taken by three PPI projects. By reading this document, interested stakeholders might be able to identify which are the main practices followed by

successful PCP and PPI projects in the past and assess if they are worthy to be implemented in their innovative procurement procedures. This document does not intend, however, to provide an exhaustive presentation of the PCP and PPI projects analysed. Thus, we recommend further reading of the documents produced by these projects, as some challenges and solutions found by them are described in these documents. A list of sources can be found at the end of this document, which will facilitate the search and reading. We want, finally, to provide a last note: the analysis presented in this document is based on the availability of documents publicly describing the actions taken by the projects. With this said, the reader shall be aware that although some projects seem to have not taken some specific action, this can be due to the lack of further descriptions provided by the projects.

Figure 1: Main phases of procurement for innovation (PCP and PPI)

2. PCP ANALYSIS

IMAILE was the first Pre-Commercial Procurement project in Europe in the field of Education. From 2014 to 2018, the four procurers involved in this EU co-funded project identified several needs related to an increased demand of personalized learning and accordingly challenged the learning technology market announcing a joint PCP call for tenders. The project resulted in two smart and innovative Personal Learning Environments (PLE) offering Learning Analytics provided by intelligent tutoring systems to primary and secondary schools that no other solutions available on the market offer.

DOMAIN: Education. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** Halmstad municipality (SE), Ministry of Finance of Saxony Anhalt (DE), City council of Viladecans (ES), Municipality of Konnevesi (FI). | **WEBSITE:** <http://www.imaile.eu/> ; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619231>

Helix Nebula Science Cloud (HNSciCloud) was a PCP project for the establishment of a European hybrid cloud platform to support the deployment of high-performance computing and bigdata capabilities for scientific research. HNSciCloud was sponsored by 10 of Europe's leading public research organisations and co-funded by the European Commission. It won Procura+Award.

DOMAIN: Public Administration. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** European Organization for Nuclear Research CERN (CH), National Institute for Nuclear Physics INFN (IT), German Electron-Synchrotron DESY (DE), National Center for Scientific Research CNRS (FR), Karlsruhe Institute for Technology KIT (DE), SURFsara (NL), Science and Technology Facilities Council STFC (UK), European Molecular Biology Laboratory EMBL-EBI (DE), Institute for High Energy Physics IFAE (ES), European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). | **WEBSITE:** <https://www.hnscicloud.eu/> ; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/687614>

SILVER (Supporting Independent LiVing for the Elderly through Robotics) was a PCP project funded by the European Commission, which main aim was to identify new technologies and services to support the independent living of the elderly, through the establishment and execution of an agreed Pre-Commercial Procurement process.

DOMAIN: Health. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** City of Eindhoven (NL), City of Odense (DK), City of Oulu (FI), City of Stockport (UK), City of Vantaa (FI), City of Västerås (SE), Region of Southern Denmark (DK). | **WEBSITE:** <https://www.silverpcp.eu/> ; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/287609>

PRACE-3IP was designed to continue, extend and complement the previous and on-going work in the implementation phase of the PRACE Research Infrastructure. Twenty six partners collaborated in this EU co-funded project. In 2018, the project delivered three pilot solutions that use different technology approaches that improve the state-of-the art of more energy efficient high performance computing.

DOMAIN: Energy. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** CINECA (IT), Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH (DE), Genci (FR), EPCC (UK), CSC (FI). | **WEBSITE:** <https://prace-ri.eu/about/jp-projects/#PRACE3IP> ; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/312763>

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	PHASE 0	PHASE 1	PHASE 2	PHASE 3
IMAILE	14 Months	5 Months	9 Months	12 Months
HNSCICLOUD	9 Months	5 Months	8 Months	10 Months
SILVER	7 Months	6 Months	12 Months	12 Months
PRACE-3IP	> 13 Months	6 Months	10 Months	16 Months

GET TO KNOW PCP
[WATCH LEA VIDEO](#)
 => [PCP IN 5 STEPS](#)

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | NEEDS ANALYSIS

IMAILE

Actions: Surveys; WIBGI Workshops; Desktop Research. Target audiences: end-users: Procurers; Teachers; Students; Organisations working in the field of education.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Surveys shall be short and easy to answer. Better results when “interviewers” are close to the respondents (e.g. same region). In IMAILE, teachers and students answered surveys.
- ◆ Interactive workshop with schools shall focus on the needs, problems and future visions.
- ◆ The common need has to be clearly understood by all procurers in all countries and all languages: the need analysis is the foundation of the Challenge Brief – the core of ITT documents.
- ◆ KPI shall be agreed to feed the Challenge Brief.
- ◆ User-driven and demand-driven innovations shall not be mixed up, as, alone, end-users cannot provide sufficient input to create an innovation that meets demand of a complete EU market and Education sector. The inclusion of EU experts is recommended.
- ◆ To involve teachers from EU level networks, attending events such as SCIENTIX are encouraged.

WIBGI =
“Wouldn’t It
Be Great If”
Workshops

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: Workshop (simultaneously online and physical). It was immediately preceded by a workshop targeting suppliers. Target audiences: end-users: Procurers.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ No specific lesson learned was identified by the project to this phase. However, it is possible to retrieve some lessons and/ or inspirations from the workshop organised. It had 2 parts: in the first one, procurers analyzed and discussed the different requirements of the project. From these requirements, different use cases were identified. In the second part of the workshop, procurers were asked to score the use cases, based on their value for the end-user. A “planning poker” methodology was used. This methodology allows

to estimate the added value, level of complexity, required implementation effort or risk.

- ◆ The assessments made by procurers were combined with the suppliers’ evaluation. By combining both scores, it was possible to assess the innovation potential of a use case.

SILVER

Actions: No detailed description of the actions taken was found.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Sufficient time for this phase shall be allocated for both individual analyses within each country, and for coordinating and consolidating a common understanding of the cross-national needs. In SILVER, needs assessment took more time than it was expected. SILVER did a needs assessment within elderly care, where the structure and level of service vary greatly from country to country. A shared understanding among partners, and data from the different organizations, had to be established.
- ◆ It is also recommended to examine, during this phase, what needs the PCP processes fulfil within the organisations of the contracting authorities.
- ◆ It is important to give room for different approaches and target groups within the countries. Preferably using both quantitative and qualitative methods and involvement. However, it is important to decide upfront on what questions need to be answered, and how the consortium will analyse the gathered information.

PRACE-3IP

In PRACE-3IP, the needs analysis was conducted before the project was funded by the European Commission. No detailed documentation was found on the project website describing that process

Market Analysis / Prior art analysis: After needs analysis, EAFIP recommends to conduct a state of the art analysis (identification of existing products, ongoing product development and published ideas, whether IPR protected or not) to confirm if the identified needs are indeed “unmet” needs. In IMAILE, it was implemented a desktop research and strengths and weaknesses analysis to assess different kinds of ICT-based solutions, taking into account the identified needs.

Note: Some projects report the “Open Market Consultation” process as corresponding to Phase 0. For this reason, information concerning the needs analysis from the demand side might be found on these reports.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | OPEN MARKET CONSULTATION (OMC)

IMAILE

Actions: Surveys; Participation in events; Meetings; Workshops; PIN (Prior Information Notice); Desktop Research.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Due to its heterogeneity and diversity, learning technology requires a different OMC approach than more segmented and specific markets. Instead of inviting potential suppliers to one or two separated industrial PCP workshops, IMAILE adopted a “Go to meet” approach at already established EU events (e.g. *Online Educa Berlin* (OEB), *BETT in London* and *European Conference for Technology-Enhanced Learning* (EC-TEL)) to achieve a larger outreach and dialogue.
- ◆ A clear strategy for OMC shall be developed. IMAILE’s “Four As” methodology is encouraged to be used.
- ◆ Information needs to be transparent, published on the website (same information for all in Q&A).
- ◆ A supplier information package (SIP) is recommended. The SIP shall include initial information on the PCP call and suppliers’ benefits.
- ◆ A strategy to promote the call shall be designed and transparently shared with the target audiences, identifying the appropriate channels, the timetable, the communication, and tasks flow among the parties involved, as well as the process of feedback collection.
- ◆ Attract the suppliers’ procurement – size and co-creation of R&I.
- ◆ Working in stages is advisable (RFI I and RFI II), as the PCP is a new tool for suppliers.
- ◆ RFI can be used to create assessment criteria.

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: PIN; Workshop (simultaneously online and physical). It was immediately preceded by a workshop targeting the procurers.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ No specific lesson learned was identified by the project to this phase. However, it is possible to retrieve some lessons and/ or inspirations from the workshop organised. In here, suppliers were asked to identify and estimate the risks for each of the use cases previously identified by procurers (see the section concerning the needs analysis). A “planning poker” methodology was used. This

methodology allows to estimate the added value, level of complexity, required implementation effort or risk. The assessments made by suppliers were combined with the procurers’ evaluation. By combining both scores, it was possible to assess the innovation potential of a use case. The workshop was recorded and made available on the Project website.

SILVER

Actions: Online questionnaire; Participation in events; Mailing to relevant stakeholders; PIN.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Having an online OMC questionnaire open for 4 weeks can give enough responses. In SILVER, it was open from Sept. to Oct. 2012. It was published in the Supplement to the Official Journal of the European Union (OJ/S) in Sept. 2012.
- ◆ E-mails were sent to promote the questionnaire, mostly to national (robotics) networks, companies, universities, intermediates, etc. It was asked to forward the e-mails to relevant networks, people and companies all over Europe that could be interested.
- ◆ The participation in an already existing event, where a target group is represented, is worth considering. SILVER participated at *AAL Forum, Eindhoven* to inform about the project, the OMC and have some discussions.
- ◆ An open and objective approach is important to get a good view of what is already available.

PRACE-3IP

Actions: Workshop (including a request for written feedback from suppliers).

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Organising a public workshop allowed the Group of Procurers to get feedback from the suppliers concerning the different aspects of the planned PCP (technical and process aspects). The technical goals presented during this meeting were chosen to be both comprehensive and informative enough to

ensure a concise discussion of the technical and commercial viability by the participants with the organisers. Two Q&A sessions were organised. All invited vendors, i.e. not only the participating ones, were encouraged to provide written feedback after the meeting, which resulted in a list of suggestions and recommendations from the suppliers.

- ◆ Promotion of workshop worldwide: PRACE web site, HPCwire and invitations sent to PROSPECT (a European association promoting High-Performance Computing — HPC) and the ETP4HPC members.

Attracting stakeholders:

PRACE-3IP created a pilot – SHAPE – intended to support SME and addressing the following barriers to HPC adoption:

- ◆ Lack of expertise and/or knowledge on the possibilities of HPC and advanced numerical simulation;
- ◆ Lack of resources to facilitate the HPC adoption process;
- ◆ The entry costs of implementing new technologies. To support European SMEs, SHAPE will develop an integrated service offer:
 - ◆ Information and networking;
 - ◆ Access to expertise (science-domain expertise as well as applied mathematics, HPC and computer science expertise);
 - ◆ Access to HPC systems (including pre- and post-processing and computing services);
 - ◆ Access to funding sources.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | TENDER DOCUMENTATION, LAUNCH AND ASSESSMENT

IMAILE

Actions: Production of ITT documentation; Launch of ITT / Call on TED; Q&A; Tender Information Session; Assessment of proposals received.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Invitation to Tender (ITT) shall be developed in parallel with need analysis and open market consultation to be effective.
- ◆ Templates from other PCPs might be useful to produce the Invitation to Tender (ITT) documentation. The engagement of legal and technical expertise is recommended to support the procurers.
- ◆ Suppliers might be involved to develop innovative ways to measure and identify user cases (reduction of time, resources, increased quality etc.). These cases shall be included as business cases in Challenge brief.
- ◆ The “wish-list” on the Challenge Brief might be specific, including pedagogical, technical, and financial benefits.
- ◆ Before launching the call, all procurers shall understand and accept the Challenge Brief.
- ◆ A User rights clause needs to be included in the IPR section for future deployment by the procurers.
- ◆ The inclusion of open standards as minimum requirements is advisable to avoid national legislations and requirements for deployment and purchase.
- ◆ PCP phases length: 1) 4 months, 2) 8 months and 3) 12 months.
- ◆ A demo/mockup as the output of phase 1 is recommended.
- ◆ More interaction/collaboration between the procurers and suppliers shall occur in phase 2. Phase 2 timeline needs to be larger to ensure that prototypes are ready for testing in real classrooms in phase 3.
- ◆ A clear communication scheme between procurers and suppliers from phase 1-3 shall be designed to ensure formal dialogue.
- ◆ Each PCP phase needs to be broken down into smaller packages of features and work for agile management and monitoring for suppliers and procurers Ex. Phase 2 packages to demonstrate specific features followed by the Phase 3 test phase to test the same features.
- ◆ Before launching the call, it is recommended to organise a workshop addressing only PCP information (ITT).
- ◆ IMAILE provided the following set of documents to the operators that could tender in the PCP: ITT; Challenge Brief; Tender Form; Guidance for filling the tender form; Q&A document; Framework

Agreement; Phase Contracts – Work Orders; Assessment criteria; Progress interim report form; End of phase report and service offer for upcoming phase template form; Invitation to Information Meeting.

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: Production of ITT documentation; Launch of ITT / Call; Contract Notice on OJEU; Q&A about tender documents; Tender Information Session; Assessment of proposals received; Award Ceremony.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Nominating a lead procurer that already had longstanding relationships with all members of the buyers' group proved a successful approach in HNSciCloud. Regular and intense interaction between the members of the buyers' group as well as between the buyers' group and the contractors has been an important element of the success of HNSciCloud.
- ◆ In the tender text, it is recommended to include a restriction forbidding a company from being a lead contractor and a participant in other bidding consortia. No more than one tender can be submitted by a natural or legal entity
- ◆ It is advisable to add provisions in the selection criteria to ensure that proposed solutions by competing consortia are sufficiently distinct and multiple solutions for each PCP challenges are developed.
- ◆ Strive to contract a higher number of consortia during each phase to ensure sufficient competition and increase the likelihood of successful completion.
- ◆ Intermediate reviews and payments shall be scheduled as important checkpoints for the buyers' group and contractors, to ensure all parties remained active and engaged.

SILVER

Actions: Production of ITT documentation; Launch of ITT / Call; PIN; Tender on OJEU; Q&A about tender documents; Assessment of proposals received; Contract Award Notice.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Defining the challenge is fundamental for the success of a PCP. The challenge should address the needs of intended end-users and be described in a way that engages the market in delivering solutions

HNSciCloud's
>Tender Information
Session<

that can create the desired benefits. SILVER worked with a broad challenge definition (instead of a narrow definition) to lead to ideas that were unconventional and truly innovative within the complex field of elderly care. This resulted in broad functional requirements, which made it challenging to communicate them accurately. However, in SILVER the experience was that the companies/tenderers responded well to the broad challenge description and functional requirements and the received proposals showed a high level of innovation at this early stage.

- ◆ Learning from SILVER shows the importance of aligning expectations concerning the level of prototypes in Phase 2 and 3 with the contractors so that they know in advance what is expected from their product (development) further on in the project. The contractual arrangements describing the R&D services to be provided by the awardees, including the operational context where and how the Phase 3 testing is executed, shall be made available to all interested bidders since the beginning to enable them to formulate the offer.
- ◆ Learning regarding legal issues in SILVER has shown that the legal framework is probably one of the most challenging tasks when performing a transnational PCP. It is considered of absolute importance to carry out national legal checks by legal experts.
- ◆ To ensure that the IPR considerations are addressed sufficiently it may be valuable to include an expert on IPR in the project consortium.
- ◆ For the PCP-call in SILVER "ceiling-price" combined with "price" of proposals was used as an assessment criterion. This resulted in some initially "low priced" proposals, which could influence the ranking of less capable solutions.
- ◆ A formal Q&A function on the project website and nominated contact points to handle this function may be valuable tools for communicating necessary details.
- ◆ SILVER provided the following set of documents to the operators that could tender in the PCP: ITT; Challenge Brief; Guidance for filling the tender form; Tender Form; Q&A document; Framework Agreement; End of Phase Report Form; Invitation to Information Meeting.
- ◆ In the assessment of the bids, SILVER used a large panel of external experts with different fields of expertise to participate in the Decision Panel with the procurers. In the assessment process, it is important to consider how many expert assessors and what types of expertise are necessary to ensure a suitable representation of the PCP project in its entirety. It is also relevant to consider, whether all expert assessor rankings should be weighted the same within each criterion based

on their fields of expertise. These decisions may have a significant impact on the final ranking of proposals.

- ◆ Provision of instructions to bids' evaluators is crucial, as they need to understand the assessment criteria. It was provided with the following documents: Guidance for Assessors; Score Sheet.
- ◆ Formal rules for announcements of contracts awarded shall be followed. In SILVER winning proposals of the PCP, a call was published on the project website and project partners' own websites. Finally, a "Contract Award Notice" was announced on the formal EU procurement system.
- ◆ When doing a PCP across different partners and countries, it is advisable to design a dissemination plan including activities on both European and national level. A person should be assigned for following-up on the dissemination activities and documenting them.
- ◆ Cross-national cooperation takes time, and this has to be considered when planning the preparation phase for launching a cross-border PCP. The project partners and participants in SILVER were from different backgrounds and countries, what make the process of getting a joint understanding of PCP longer than it was expected. The language was also a barrier in some occasions, leading to miscommunication. An efficient and flexible virtual platform for meetings and communication is a great help.

PRACE-3IP

Actions: Production of ITT documentation; Launch of ITT / Call; Contract Notice; Tender Information Session; Assessment of proposals received; Signature of the framework agreement and the contract for phase 1.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ In PRACE-3IP, it was created a specific team to manage the tendering phase. It was led by the PCP Coordinator and Deputy Coordinator and included a set of technical and legal experts delegated by the PRACE-3IP partners involved in the PCP.
- ◆ The call was published in EU TED web site, the Italian Official Journal (Gazzetta Ufficiale), the tender web site of the procuring entity, and the websites of the group of procurers.
- ◆ It was provided with the following set of documents to the operators that could tender in the PCP: Tender Regulation document; Tender Technical Requirements; Framework Agreement; PCP Contract for Phase I, II, and III; PCP End of Phase Report Form.
- ◆ It was created the following set of documents to be used by the assessment team: Guidelines for Assessors; Evaluation Criteria.
- ◆ To avoid illegal state aid, the procuring authority should calculate in advance the maximum price it will pay for the R&D services based

on a calculation of the price paid for exclusive development when the procurer keeps all the benefits. Another good practice is to ask bidding companies to supply the calculation of the price reduction they can offer in return for the IPR benefits and include a financial

expert in the PCP tender evaluation committee who is charged with assessing whether the business cases and associated price reductions for the IPRs offered by different companies are indeed in line with normal market conditions in that sector.

PHASE 1 – EXECUTION - SOLUTION DESIGN

IMAILE

Actions: Definition of a Contract Manager; Q&A document; Face to face meetings and try out sessions; Success Criteria Table (SCT); Confidence Criteria Table (CCT); Assessment of suppliers progress.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ The function of a Contract manager (CM) is recommended to support the management team and procurers. The CM shall monitor the appliance of contracts and Service offers and the procurers and technical manager shall monitor to the content of the PCP based upon the Challenge Brief.
- ◆ Contract management reports shall be official EC deliverables as they are evidence on how the investments are monitored.
- ◆ The contract and reporting methodology shall be simplified according to the suppliers of IMAILE.
- ◆ To plan the Evaluation stage the work needs to be prepared simultaneously as the ITT documentation is being prepared and it needs to be defined and agreed among all parties minimum 3 months before launching the PCP call. The "Evaluation panel Guidance" shall include a detailed description and sets the rules of the game of the evaluation process. It is a roadmap for all procurers in the evaluation process of bids/proposals received during the PCP process (Phase 1, 2 and 3) as well as for the Evaluation panel. The document defines its composition, roles and responsibilities of all members. It also details the evaluation process, the assessment criteria and weighting, as well as if Blind evaluation and majority decision are applied.
- ◆ The composition of the evaluation panels shall be heterogeneous, with local/regional experts and EU experts for best results both to satisfy the investing procurers and to guarantee a "beyond user perspective" of the investments. It is recommended to be composed by Tendering board and lead procurer; Expert Board, Local Assessors and Expert board leader; Contract manager.
- ◆ The stimulation of dialogue from Phase 1 is advisable, using tools like Success Criteria Table (SCT) and Confidence Criteria table (CCT). In phase 1, IMAILE recommends setting up a formal dialogue on two occasions.
- ◆ A think tank panel can be installed with different experts beyond user experience to strengthen the dialogue between procurers and suppliers.

- ◆ The technical manager is important to create a common language between demand and supply side and a common understanding during the dialogue.
- ◆ The most important steering document for dialogue is the Challenge Brief.

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: Definition of a Monitoring Team (MT), composed of buyers' group's members; Regular meetings among buyers group members and between MT and suppliers' group. Deliverables asked contractors: project abstract and list of pre-existing IPs; technical deliverables; and non-technical deliverables.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ The Buyers Group should prepare detailed information about each use-case before the tender is launched, including the desired performance and any technical constraints;
- ◆ An owner who is capable of responding to questions should be identified for each use-case;
- ◆ The dialogue between the Buyers Groups and the Contractors should start at the beginning of the phase and be maintained during the whole period;
- ◆ An intermediate milestone during which each Contractor presents their progress should be foreseen;
- ◆ The buyers' Group effort planning should be revised when the Request for Tender is published to take into account the number of milestones and deliverables to be assessed as well as the need for a continuous dialogue with the Contractors;
- ◆ A dedicated technical team shall be established to collect input from all procurers on use-cases, requirements, interact with the contractors and perform tests.

IMAILE's Contract manager duties:

- ◆ protect the investment;
- ◆ ensure conformance to contract;
- ◆ promote collaboration and communication;
- ◆ maintain fairness and parity;
- ◆ identify and resolve issues;
- ◆ assist and mentor the suppliers; assist the procurers.

In IMAILE, CM was requested to produce: CM Baseline report at the beginning of each PCP phase; CM Midpoint Monitoring report at the midpoint of each PCP phase; and a CM End of Phase report at the end of each PCP phase.

SILVER

Actions: Identification of a Project Monitoring officer (PMO) from the SILVER consortium; Regular contacts between PMO and suppliers' group and provided support from PMO to procurers group during assessment periods; Assignment of procurers able to answer suppliers questions. Answers shared in a public Q&A document; Involvement of end-users through surveys; Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys); Call documents and assessment of bids.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ The involvement of end-users in Phase 1 is relevant. Suppliers/ contractors may be encouraged to do this with the help of a third party or to make a survey themselves. The Procurers/ Project consortium may consider assisting the contractors e.g. by hosting co-creation sessions. In a transnational PCP, the use of international personas (i.e. representation of intended users) may further enable the solutions to meet possible differences between countries.
- ♦ In SILVER, PMO was the main contact with suppliers, which made the flow of information and contact more protected and standardised. You can also choose to include the contractors in relevant meetings with the other participants e.g. in the discussion of the testing procedures and facilitate the contact with the procurers.
- ♦ In SILVER the importance of agreeing on expectations for Phase 2 testing (purpose, criteria, scope, timeline, testing tasks etc.) within the consortium before Phase 2 starts became clear. A detailed testing description should be included in the contracts for Phase 2, including details regarding e.g. purpose, strategy, approach, criteria, scope, timeline (including planning process), test user description, test tasks, risk schedule, insurance, data privacy, ethics and confidentiality. This may help manage expectations between the contractor and the consortium upfront.
- ♦ The assessment questionnaire sent to suppliers was a good learning as they appreciated the effort to get their input for the process.

PRACE-3IP

Actions: Assignment of a team responsible for follow-up suppliers work; Monitoring Visits; Call documents and assessment of bids.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ In PRACE-3IP, the Group of Procurers organised the work in the following way: a steering group, called the GoP Committee, has been established to oversee the process and to make any decisions regarding the PCP. The execution of the actual procurement had to be done by CINECA acting as the Procuring Entity. Work

package 8 (WP8) and task 2.1 (T2.1) of PRACE-3IP have laid the groundwork for the PCP and will provide the necessary workforce to implement the PCP process. The evaluation of the PCP results, as well as the initial tenders, will be performed by an Assessment Committee with the support of WP8. To coordinate the whole process and to serve as a link between the GoP Committee and the implementation team, a Coordinator will be appointed by the GoP Committee and to assist him a Deputy Coordinator will be appointed by the Procuring Entity.

- ♦ At the middle of Phase I, it was planned to perform monitoring visits. These visits enabled the procurers to get an understanding of the progress made so far and to potentially identify issues which block Contractors on their path towards innovative solutions to the problems defined within this PCP.
- ♦ Contractors must present an analysis that shows that a sustainable market for the technology developed within the PCP exists from the end of the project onwards. In PRACE-3IP, a set of overall technical criteria and corresponding weights have been defined to assess the bids provided not only during the Tendering Stage, as well as during Phase I and II: Quality of R&D and level of innovation (30%); Technical requirements compliance (20%); Progress in terms of energy efficiency (30%); Project quality and feasibility (20%). The technical quality of the bids was evaluated based on a set of technical documents which the bidders were requested to submit: Technology concepts; High-level architecture and pilot system description; Power-efficiency analysis; Work-plan for phase 1, 2 and 3; Risk analysis; Market analysis from 2017 onwards; Critical components supply documentation; Human resources and place of performance documentation. This technical documentation must be at a level of detail that allows an assessment of the compliance of the proposed solution with the technical requirements. Furthermore, for each of these technical documents one or more criteria have been defined to rate both the quality of the solution as well as the quality of the technical documentation that was provided.
- ♦ Contractors shall provide technical documentation, containing all information that is needed to apply the technical evaluation criteria. In PRACE-3IP, the contractors were requested to submit the following documents: Technology design specifications; High-level architecture and pilot system design specification; Definition of targets for execution time and energy consumption; Detailed work plan for phase II and III; Business plan for the pilot system; Risk analysis for reaching targets at the end of Phase III; Market analysis from 2017 onwards; Human resources and place of performance documentation.

PHASE 1

Tender Budget:

IMAILE: 10%

HNSCICLOUD: 15%

SILVER: 16%

PRACE-3IP: 10%

PHASE 2

Tender Budget:

IMAILE: 40%

HNSCICLOUD: 25%

SILVER: 33%

PRACE-3IP: 30%

PHASE 3

Tender Budget:

IMAILE: 50%

HNSCICLOUD: 60%

SILVER: 50%

PRACE-3IP: 60%

PHASE 2 – EXECUTION - PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

IMAILE

Actions: See actions in Phase 1, as actions taken were like those described in that section.

Lessons Learned: See lessons learned in Phase 1. Besides those lessons, in phase 2, IMAILE recommends setting up a formal dialogue on three occasions involving end-users (focus groups from need analysis).

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: Monitoring of contractors' activities; Extensive testing of prototype solutions; Meetings and progress review events.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Precise definitions of key technical requirements including examples/ user stories should be provided during the earlier stages of the project.
- ◆ Feature freeze periods must be enforced more strictly, both in the tender documentation and during the project execution.
- ◆ A ticketing system and shared collaboration tool between the buyers' group and each contractor should be put in place at the very beginning of the phase.
- ◆ A single point of access to all procurers' documentation is needed.
- ◆ Foreseen IaaS capacity and cloud resource utilisation should be planned carefully. Tender documentation should describe a solution in case not all of the resource was utilized due to delays.
- ◆ The involvement of the same partners, subcontractors or technologies in multiple bids should be avoided to ensure the solutions developed within the PCP are sufficiently distinct.

SILVER

Actions: Regular contacts between PMO and suppliers group; Organisation of meeting between SILVER consortium members and suppliers at the beginning of Phase 2; Answers to suppliers' questions shared in a public Q&A document; Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys); Phase 2 testing process; Call documents and assessment of bids.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ When the Q&A process is used, all relevant project partners shall be involved in a discussion so to mutually agree on the answers to be provided.

- ◆ In Phase 2 of the SILVER PCP, experience from both the SILVER partners and the contractors show that cooperation and dialogue between the procurers and contractors throughout a PCP can be essential, e.g. to: ensure that the future needs of the end-users are addressed; ensure that the management of the projects and the PCP process at large reflects the needs of the procurers and the contractors; ensure that the development of the prototypes is going as planned; exchange ideas and input to enhance the innovation process and value of the product; discuss and clarify requests in the concept call documents.
- ◆ It is recommendable to allocate dedicated resources from the procurers to engage with the contractors from Phase 1 to provide feedback and develop a business case for procurement.
- ◆ In Phase 2 of the SILVER PCP, it was discovered that interviews with contractors before assessment of bids for the next phase could be very beneficial in ensuring that the assessors have sufficient information about the bids and the solutions. The interviews were successfully implemented in Phase 3.
- ◆ Learnings from SILVER underline the importance of reserving enough time for the preparation of the Phase 2 Prototype Tests concerning e.g: Agreement on test tasks and test user profile between procurers and contractors; Agreement on assessment criteria and how to assess them; Ethics (especially about medical devices); Safety and mitigation strategy (including expectations for the risk and mitigation preparations of the contractors); Timeline (communicate deadlines and expectations to contractors well in advance so that they know what is expected when and can plan accordingly); Setting up the test environment.
- ◆ The Phase 2 Test Team in SILVER found it highly valuable to visit the contractors while planning the Prototype Tests.
- ◆ The Phase 2 Test Reports were considered good counterparts to the End of Phase Reports as they included more details about the performance of the prototypes, the potential of the solutions, and the issues discovered in the Phase 2 Tests. The reports may provide a good basis for assessing the Phase 2 results.
- ◆ In SILVER, unanimity in the Decision Panel was needed in assessment of the bids for Phase 3. This may result in time-consuming discussions. If unanimity is demanded in the assessment of bids method, experience from SILVER shows that the following precautions may have the potential to reduce the time of the discussions: A pre-meeting between procurers before the Decision Panel meeting to form an idea of the procurers' scores and "level of feeling"

regarding the solutions; 1:1 pre-meetings between Project Management and procurers before the Decision Panel meeting to discuss “level of feeling”

- ♦ To minimise the expenses of the contractors it is possible to implement a short tender period between phases. In this case, the contractors may need to prepare for writing the bids for Phase 3, using an early draft of the call documents before the final call for bids is published, to make sure that they have enough time.
- ♦ If one criterion (such as time-savings in SILVER) has a higher weighting than the other criteria this may have a large impact on the final scores of the bids. The learning from SILVER is that it should be considered whether the PCP will benefit from questions with a significant impact.
- ♦ Phase 2 testing process was performed by one of the SILVER partners. Each contractor had two full days of testing – one day of safety testing by the partner Test team and experts from care institutions, followed by one day of usability testing by end-users

PRACE-3IP

Actions: Monitoring suppliers work; Call documents and assessment of bids.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Contractors shall provide technical documentation, containing all information that is needed to apply the technical evaluation criteria. In PRACE-3IP, the contractors were requested to submit the following documents: Technology design specifications update; Updated architecture and pilot system design specification; Specification of execution time and energy consumption; Detailed work plan for phase III; Pilot system deployment plan; Risk analysis

for reaching targets at end of Phase III; Market analysis from 2018 onwards; Human resources and place of performance documentation.

PHASE 3 – EXECUTION - ORIGINAL DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING

IMAILE

Actions: See actions in Phase 1, as actions taken were like those described in that section. Besides those actions, in this phase, IMAILE implemented a testing process in real classrooms.

Lessons Learned: See lessons learned in Phase 1. Besides those lessons:

- ♦ In phase 3, IMAILE advises having a formal dialogue on 3 occasions, along with ongoing tests with informal dialogue for one year.
- ♦ A properly preparation for evaluation with end-users in real classrooms shall be carried on, strengthened by “beyond user experience” EU experts.
- ♦ The focus shall be on quality instead of quantity. Smaller groups and amounts of students are recommended for longer testing periods and it is important to keep the same test groups throughout the phase.
- ♦ Empirical studies and observation for Primary schools (no test surveys) are recommended.
- ♦ Teachers and students might be motivated to participate with certificates, study visits and peer support. It is advisable to provide an additional budget for schools. IMAILE recommends providing one teacher work week (1 day/week) per supplier for qualitative test results.
- ♦ The tests shall be divided into several “sprints” enabling risk management and close monitoring: Start-up phase; Installations and pre-test phase, permission to test from procurers; First testing phase; Interim collecting data and analysis; Second testing phase; Final collecting data and analysis.
- ♦ Phase 3 testing requires interaction with real users, many of whom will be children. These users must be protected.

HNSCICLOUD

Actions: Regular meetings among buyers group members and with suppliers’ group; Participation in events to disseminate project pilot services; Organisation of training events. Phase 3 was divided into two sub-phases, each one coordinated by different project’s partners.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Weekly meetings between Buyers Groups and contractors proved to be very fruitful to address the issues raised during testing of use-cases. The organisation of formal progress reviews, scheduled

during the execution phase of the PCP, provide decision points that ensure the results of the project are relevant for procurers.

- ♦ Reorientation of solutions is simpler to implement during the transition between phases than within a phase of execution.
- ♦ A service conformance test-suite that can be executed by contractors without external support simplifies the development and deployment process.
- ♦ A market readiness assessment is necessary to ensure all the support activities to bring a service to market are in place. A service providers’ self-assessment of the Technology Readiness Level is not sufficient, and some external assessment is required for widespread production usage.
- ♦ For large-scale production usage, data flows need to be understood in advance to establish the full network connectivity requirements.
- ♦ A common approach for a proxy service and group/role/authZ attribute management mapping should be foreseen in the context of EduGAIN.
- ♦ Cloud service migration and exit strategies are essential and should be addressed in the cloud service agreement.
- ♦ An agreed mechanism for identifying and recording service outages is necessary.
- ♦ Open source interface packages, such as Terraform and Libcloud, simplify the porting of applications between cloud services and reduce the reliance cloud technical brokers.
- ♦ Exchanges of resource quotas facilitate scalability testing and increase added value for procurers.
- ♦ The exchange of quotas between the Buyers Group voluntarily proved to be essential to perform larger-scale tests.
- ♦ It is recommended to set-up a testing environment and procedures to validate software components in advance.
- ♦ The registration of the pilot services in the unified European Open Science Cloud online service catalogue potentially improves the visibility of the commercial cloud providers.
- ♦ Voucher schemes can promote the adoption of the new services to end-users for limited scale usage.
- ♦ Widely recognised performance metrics should be included as part of the assessment of cloud services.
- ♦ In future PCP projects, it is suggested that Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) studies should be a deliverable of each phase (design,

prototype and pilot) with increasing accuracy as chosen use-cases progress towards deployment.

- ♦ The Buyers Group and contractors should regularly monitor the consumption of cloud resources and make adjustments accordingly to ensure all the objectives can be achieved.
- ♦ The Pre-Commercial Procurement instrument does not adequately support the pay-as-you-go model for resource consumption.
- ♦ The stakeholders should reassess the total amount of resources required for each phase of the PCP project.
- ♦ Allocating sufficient resources during the design and pilot phase will simplify the execution of the pilot phase.

The network requirements for data-intensive use-cases should be established in detail during the tender preparation phase. PCP projects should include the option to purchase the resulting pilots through a license to use the final developed solution.

SILVER

Actions: Regular contacts between PMO and suppliers group; Organisation of meeting between SILVER consortium members and suppliers at the beginning of Phase 3; Organisation of meeting to prepare testing phase (try the prototype, information on the latest version), in each country; Answers to suppliers' questions shared in a public Q&A document; Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys).

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ In planning the Phase 3 testing it is considered essential to look at the previous test results as well as the PCP challenge to assess the progression of the solution and the potential to solve the challenge.
- ♦ Most of the test coordinators/ procurers and other relevant SILVER consortium members saw and tried the solution before the Phase 3 tests (meeting), which proved valuable for planning the tests.
- ♦ The overall experience with Phase 3 tests in SILVER was that it proved very valuable to involve end-users in the tests as it provided insight into how the solution worked, which functionalities were useful, the relevant target group and the overall potential of the solution.
- ♦ Learnings from SILVER show that the online meetings that followed the tests in each country were very valuable for sharing learnings and knowledge.
- ♦ When you have consecutive tests at each location as in SILVER, following up on learnings between each country test may provide

an opportunity to improve both the solution itself and the conduction of the following tests.

- ♦ National and international events during the PCP with participation by the contractor are recommendable as they create good PR opportunities for both the PCP project and the contractor and communicate valuable learnings. In SILVER most of the procuring authorities hosted national events in connection with the Phase 3 tests and the SILVER PCP project hosted an international event at the end of Phase 3. SILVER experience emphasised the importance of planning events early to allow maximum participation.
- ♦ In SILVER the development of End of Project videos proved useful for dissemination purposes.

PRACE-3IP

Actions: Monitoring suppliers work; Monitoring visits to contractors' premises; Assessment of reports.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Allowing three vendors into the PCP Phase III increased the number of activities for assessment, visits and monitoring by at least 50% to what was planned. This was especially significant considering that the three vendors were in three different countries and the location of each final pilot system was in a different country as well.
- ♦ To avoid delays in the planned schedule the hosting location of systems needs to be addressed at an early stage so it is settled before the last phase is launched. The Procurers need to agree on the sites where the prototypes will be installed and also under which conditions this will be done.
- ♦ A stronger decision-making process would have helped to avoid delays in the whole procedure. A suggestion might be that the EC, perhaps via an expert representing their interests, become a member of the GoP (as a co-founder) to accelerate decision making.
- ♦ In PRACE-3IP, contractors were requested to deliver an end-of-phase report. The structure of this report was defined in the Framework Agreement as follows: Formal questions; Documentation of results; Installed and operational pilot system; Updated performance and energy consumption models; Final market analysis: final analysis of the market.

3. OVERVIEW ACTIONS IMPLEMENTED BY PCP PROJECTS

Find, below, where you can find more information and detailed activities' planning on the different PCP phases. As stated in the introduction, in this analysis we present the information that was available in public documents; some projects might not be listed as taking part of some actions, because there was no information shared by the projects about these actions.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Needs Analysis:

- ♦ Surveys
- ♦ Workshops/ WIBGI Workshops
- ♦ Desktop Research

=> Target audiences: end-users

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Market Analysis:

- ♦ Desktop Research
- ♦ Strengths and weaknesses analysis

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Open Market Consultation:

- ♦ Surveys
- ♦ Participation in events
- ♦ Meetings
- ♦ Workshops
- ♦ PIN (Prior Information Notice)
- ♦ Desktop Research

=> Target audiences: suppliers

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Tender Documentation, Launch and Assessment:

- ♦ Production of ITT documentation
- ♦ Publication of ITT / Call
- ♦ Q&A about tender documents:
- ♦ Tender Information Session
- ♦ Assessment of proposals
- ♦ Contract Award Notice
- ♦ Award ceremony
- ♦ Signature of a framework agreement and the contract for phase 1

PHASE 1 – EXECUTION - SOLUTION DESIGN

- ♦ Definition of a Monitoring Team
- ♦ Q&A document
- ♦ Regular meetings with suppliers
- ♦ Organisation of surveys targeting end-users
- ♦ List of deliverables/ reports requested to suppliers
- ♦ Criteria and assessment of suppliers progress

PHASE 2 – EXECUTION - PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

- ♦ Monitoring of contractors' progress
- ♦ Q&A document
- ♦ Regular meetings with suppliers
- ♦ Organisation of prototype solutions' testing
- ♦ Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys)
- ♦ List of deliverables/ reports requested to suppliers
- ♦ Criteria and assessment of suppliers progress

PHASE 3 – EXECUTION - ORIGINAL DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING

- ♦ Monitoring of contractors' progress
- ♦ Q&A document
- ♦ Regular meetings with suppliers
- ♦ Participation in events to disseminate project pilot services
- ♦ Organisation of training events
- ♦ Organisation of testing process
- ♦ Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys)
- ♦ List of deliverables/ reports requested to suppliers
- ♦ Criteria and assessment of suppliers progress

4. PPI ANALYSIS

HAPPI project (Healthy Ageing – Public Procurement of Innovation) is an EU co-financed project within the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme (CIP) which aims at detecting and purchasing innovative solutions addressing the needs of an ageing society to disseminate them in hospitals and nursing homes across Europe. The innovative nature of the project not only refers to buying innovative goods but also to using innovative purchasing techniques and processes. The consortium of public buyers launched a joint cross-border public tender for the procurement of innovative goods and services for active and healthy ageing for the award of a framework agreement (open procedure) with a single economic operator (per lot) for one year with the possibility to extend the contract 3 times for one year each, division into 5 technical lots. Following these activities, the partners of the project, and more precisely, the 5 purchasers of the consortium which were Central Purchasing Bodies from 5 different countries (France, UK, Luxembourg, Italy and Belgium), prepared and launched the first European joint transnational public tender of the Healthcare sector in September 2014.

DOMAIN: Health. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** GIP Réseau des acheteurs hospitaliers d'Ile de France (GIP Resah-idf), SCR Piemonte, Mercur'Hosp, Fédération des Hôpitaux Luxembourgeois (FHL), NHS Commercial Solutions (NHS-CS). | **WEBSITE:** www.happiproject.eu

INNOCAT coordinated PPIs aimed to bring together a group of public and private buyers to publish a series of tenders for eco-innovative catering products, services,

and solutions. The aim was to help encourage eco-innovation in the catering sector by providing a sizeable launch market for new solutions. As part of the INNOCAT project, the Municipality of Turin committed to fostering its sustainable procurement approach, addressing two main objectives: (i) More food sustainability; (ii) More environmental sustainability.

DOMAIN: Sustainable catering. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** Resah-idf (Réseau des acheteurs hospitaliers d'Ile-de-France), The City of Turin, Environment Park Torino with ARPA Piemonte, University of Sheffield. | **WEBSITE:** www.sustainablecatering.eu

PROBIS project developed a coordinated performance-based procurement action aimed to solve real needs and improve energy efficiency, stimulating eco-innovation in technologies, techniques and materials and, above all, new integrated approaches and solutions in the construction sector.

The main goal of the EU project PROBIS was to use the leverage of public demand to stimulate the construction market to develop or improve new integrated approaches and solutions in the construction sector, focused on buildings' refurbishment process.

DOMAIN: Sustainable construction. | **PROCURERS INVOLVED:** Resah-idf (Réseau des acheteurs hospitaliers d'Ile-de-France), The City of Turin, Environment Park Torino with ARPA Piemonte, University of Sheffield. | **WEBSITE:** www.probisproject.eu

	PHASE 0	PHASE 4
HAPPI	24 Months	4 Months
INNOCAT	21 Months	6 Months
PROBIS (Aler Bergamo)	24 Months	6 Months

GET TO KNOW PPI
[WATCH LEA VIDEO](#)
 => [PPI IN 4 STEPS](#)

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | NEEDS ANALYSIS

HAPPI

Actions:

- ♦ Meeting with the physician, healthcare assistant and hospital staff to determine customers' demand, considering common needs for all the end-users
- ♦ Sharing experiences with other CPBs in the EU.
- ♦ End-users targeted: physician, healthcare assistant, hospital staff and citizen
- ♦ [Duration: The needs analysis was released together with other preliminary activities in the first year of the project]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Given the fact that the goods needed to be in their first phase of application or marketing (and new to the procurers), the contracting authorities tried to meeting demand and supply side. For this reason, was proposed an approach that provided for the involvement of the market, of the trade associations.

INNOCAT

Actions:

To elaborate a model of school catering with low environmental impact, the following analyses were conducted:

- ♦ Elaboration of sectoral eco-innovative requirements for the future school catering service contract, because of demand analysis and baseline assessment
- ♦ Study of the climatic impact of the current eco-friendly contract for school catering service in terms of CO₂ (Carbon footprint Indicator);
- ♦ Execution Monitoring of the sustainability requirements already in force, to stimulate compliance and progress through innovation.
- ♦ To define specific indicators to objectively measure its current environmental achievements, the Chemical Laboratory of Turin Chamber of Commerce was tasked with monitoring the current school catering sector and a carbon footprint analysis of the current contract was then carried out by the University of Turin. These monitoring results represented the baseline used to identify further areas of improvement.
- ♦ End users targeted: students, personnel, and managers of 360 schools

- ♦ Duration: the need analysis was realised in combination with the study and baseline assessment during the first year of the project.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ To correctly quantify the objectives (in terms of reduction in climate-altering gas emissions) to be achieved through the procurement, the baseline needs to be calculated carefully based on real data and a vision or strategy needs to be in place (in this case the adopted Green Public Procurement (GPP) strategy).
- ♦ From an analysis of the outcomes, the totality of the choices made for the 2013/16 three-year procurement period has resulted in environmental savings and that the most significant choices were the elimination of water in plastic bottles and the use of melamine reusable tableware.
- ♦ This said it was agreed that the choices made for fruit and vegetables (to come from regional sources whenever possible) and the use of reusable tableware will have to be confirmed in future procurement specifications. Similarly, it was agreed that tap water should continue to be used in future, and low impact vehicles should also be used, especially for purposes of a reduction in fine particle emissions. It should be noted that at present particulate is regarded as the contaminant having the greatest impact in urban areas and a factor of special significance in the incidence of acute and chronic disorders of the respiratory and cardio-circulatory apparatus.

PROBIS

Actions:

- ♦ The procurement process started with a structured "desired benefits and unmet needs" assessment, based on the end-users perspective, assuring the replicability and scalability of the intervention of the procurement, due to the relevance of the potential demand dimension of PPI.
- ♦ The needs have been defined in terms of minimum functional and performance requirements and related costs, providing an executive plan as a reference and without identifying specific solutions, to encourage the active generation of application ideas and technological choices, able to optimize the complex building performance. The innovation dimension particularly lies in the process design of works execution and evaluation of the results.

- ◆ The set of process performances reported in the PROSPECTUS and PIN forms
- ◆ To describe a need in functional and performance terms, an outline of an innovation life cycle cost method is developed, that considers the cost and benefits of the innovative solution over the entire life cycle of the innovative solution. The method TLC-PE¹ (Total Life-Cycle - functional and performance description) creates associations between expected functionalities and quantified performance targets. It classifies functionalities and related performances along with the solution life-cycle phases (production, delivery, installation, use, management, maintenance and disposal) to encourage suppliers to propose solutions with higher long-term performance and lower (total life cycle) costs
- ◆ Duration: the need analysis was realised in combination with the study and baseline assessment during the first year of the project

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ As innovation procurement is aiming to obtain higher quality at a lower "total" cost of ownership (not just at the lowest price per piece), it is crucial to focus innovation towards optimizing the performance/quality and costs across the entire life-cycle of the solution.
- ◆ Before approaching the market, assessment, and focalization of the needs of the building are of the highest importance. To select offers that best meet the expected benefits/cost reductions of the executive plan, a clear definition and precise minimum functionality/performance/cost reduction requirements in the technical specifications for the PPI is required.

¹ Sara Bedin, 2012, TLC-PE method developed and implemented in Lombardy Region for PCP and PPI projects.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | MARKET ANALYSIS / PRIOR ART ANALYSIS

HAPPI

Actions:

- ♦ Meeting with a technical expert to looking for possible innovative solutions on the market
- ♦ End-users. Technical expert of the contracting authorities involved in the project
- ♦ [Duration: The market analysis was released together with other preliminary activities in the first year of the project]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ The innovation required in the subject matter of the contract highlighted the need for dialogue with the market.

INNOCAT

Actions:

- ♦ As a preparatory step, a preliminary map of the stakeholders was created to identify the subjects to be consulted: companies, suppliers, distributors, organisations, associations, i.e., all the subjects that could design, make, sell and/or supply the products and services used in providing collective catering services.
- ♦ A key objective was to promote a dialogue between the (public) demand-side and the (private) supply side, intending to identify the critical issues and the margins for improvement of collective catering services from the standpoint of environmental sustainability.
- ♦ The meetings pinpointed problems but also identified opportunities, which were taken into due account in drafting the guidelines. Market capacity was proved, for instance, in the following fields: availability of pork meat as well as DPO cured meats from Piedmont region, availability of contractors to use electric vehicles to deliver meals; possibility to extend the eco-sustainability requirement to the dishes used for special diets, which – since reusable dishes cannot be used due to technical/operational reasons – could be made of compostable materials; possibility of adopting mobility management systems providing for real-time fleet location and tracking logs.
- ♦ [Duration: The market analysis was released together with other preliminary activities in the first year of the project]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ The innovation required in the subject matter of the contract highlighted the need for analysis shared with stakeholders

PROBIS

Actions: An extensive analysis of the State of the art was delivered, assessing the weaknesses of available solutions and global approaches implemented and tangible in the market.

Therefore, PROBIS Market Innovation Dialogue had the following objectives:

- ♦ Check whether the common needs of the PROBIS pilot project can be met at the date with newly developed commercially viable end-products or with the product so close to the market that no mid-to-long term R&D but only incremental/integration type development is required;
- ♦ Trigger the supply side to activate its production chain to deliver the required innovations;
- ♦ Stimulate widespread participation of companies within public tendering (in particular innovative SMEs);
- ♦ Increase the knowledge of EU procures, enterprises and building sector players on innovative solution available on the early market.
- ♦ The engagement of the market consisted of two parallel actions – Market Innovation Surveys and Market Engagement Events.
- ♦ **Market Innovation Surveys**
- ♦ Market Innovation Surveys were online surveys with the purpose to involve the largest possible audience of stakeholders in open and transparent research on the innovative solutions for the refurbishment of buildings setting. These surveys occurring to define the baseline, have been useful to fix the challenging performance requirements of the procurements.
- ♦ **Market Engagement Events**
- ♦ Market Engagement Events were opportunities to inform the attendants about the characteristics of the building object of the tender and open a dialogue with the market operators about the performance requirements.
- ♦ [Duration: The market analysis was released together with other preliminary activities in the first year of the project]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ As it happens in any "mature" technological environment, most of the technologies for the building sector, including energy management, efficiency and renewable ones, are under a continuous upgrading process through small innovations, each of them often made and patented by a single manufacturer. The result it is a flow of new products in which is difficult to evaluate the real level of performance of the innovation(s) in term of quantifiable benefits, that could allow a rationale based comparison (e.g. it is easy to evaluate the energy saving in a building due to the improvement of the thermal transmittance of insulation material, while it is harder to estimate the real average energy saving of a

more sophisticated interactive space heating temperature controller, as well as its actual ease of use by an average user).

- ♦ Given the above, it has been decided to show the results of the outlook to the innovative solution, splitting them up by classes of technologies and development phase when possible.
- ♦ Always carefully analyse the market and the local condition to set a tender attractive enough to have large participation by the bidders. After the bidding process, it is important to show a strong commitment to award real innovation and the most economically advantageous offer. The real will and credibility of the contracting authority are crucial to the positive development of the process and to assure large participation of the bidders.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | OPEN MARKET CONSULTATION (OMC)

HAPPI

Actions:

- ◆ Were organised information days in four different countries (Austria, France, Italy and UK) in collaboration with the respective Chambers of Commerce to involve the market and to meet the possible bidders and inform them about the project, objectives, the opportunity to share their innovations and how to participate in the tender
- ◆ A platform was realised to allow economic operators to share information about the innovative solution of interest for the project
- ◆ End-users. Economic operators in the relevant markets and trade associations
- ◆ [Duration: The market consultation was released together with other preliminary activities in the first year of the project]

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ The sector in which the market assessment was performed was extremely broad, as the contracting authorities did not want to restrict the portfolio to elderly care only but invited economic operators to present innovative solutions for the entire healthcare sector.
- ◆ Submitted solutions were analysed in three parallel, simultaneous sessions in Paris, Torino and London by expert committees consisting of practitioners from hospitals and nursing homes, people working in the field daily who knew the needs of contracting authorities and understood the technical aspects of the presented solution.
- ◆ The pre-award phase offered more awareness and visibility of economic operators and their innovations in a transparent way. The platform (used to collect the innovative solution submitted by the market) offered an overview of innovative companies on the EU market and a vision of other innovative goods and services for future public procurement procedures.
- ◆ Assure the transparency of the dialogue with the market and safeguard know-how of economic operators.

INNOCAT

Actions:

In INNOCAT the analysis assumed a prior relevance, to be shared with stakeholders. Please refer to the section before

Lessons Learned: Please refer to the section before

PROBIS

Actions:

The PIN was launched before starting interactions with the market. To guarantee an effective, wide market involvement, the announcement of the tenders has been made, in addition to the institutional means, through launching and advertising conferences, press conferences, specific mailing involving the manufacturers and professional magazines and network, as well as through an open technical dialogue with the market, enabling all potential bidders to visit the operational context.

This step takes 4 months

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ The prompt service of questions answering minimized the risk of misunderstanding of the procurements aims, tenders' requirements.
- ◆ Contractors/manufacturers specialized in a single technology or group of technologies are usually not interested in acting as general contractors, in case the tender concern works not directly related to their technology, even when the other technologies are minor in terms of cost.
- ◆ Construction contractors should always be the real main target when work concerns more than one specific technology. But several contractors, especially the big ones, already have long term framework agreements with manufacturers of materials, products, and technologies, which could prevent them to investigate for the best options in the market.

HAPPI

Actions:

- ♦ The joint cross-border award procedure within the HAPPI project was based on an in-depth legal study that analysed the different possibilities offered by EU Directives for conducting the tender and defined the best contractual and organisational solution for the contracting authorities.
- ♦ A framework agreement was awarded through an open procedure under French PP law.
- ♦ The award criteria used were both price and quality.
- ♦ For each lot, the contracting authorities defined a series of technical criteria which the innovative solutions had to fulfil
- ♦ End-users.
- ♦ [Duration: The drafting of tender documents needed 5 months (April 2014/September 2014). The Publication of tender documents needed 2 months (September 2014/November 2014). The awarding procedure needed 4 months (December 2014/March 2015)]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ To allow as many bidders as possible to place an offer and to encourage their participation, the project partners decided to draft the tender documents and to conduct the procedure in three languages, namely French, Italian and English.
- ♦ Due to the coordination role of the lead buyer, the participating contracting authorities considered that they had less administrative burdens than in a procedure at the national level. There is a benefit in having just one tender procedure for all participating CPBs in terms of timesaving, even if there are complexities to deal with. The cooperation among project partners also allows to define common procurement documents available for all countries involved in the project and to overcome some of the main problems in cross-border public procurement (as languages barrier).

INNOCAT

Actions:

The layout of the specification consisted of a subdivision into “basic requirements” and “noteworthy requirements”.

The former will be used with reference to the eco-innovative solutions which confirm provisions already present in the current version of the specifications (where they may have been rated as noteworthy) or introduce minimal improvements, or else come under areas of innovation that – based on market studies - are deemed to be characterised by an appreciable degree of market maturity.

The noteworthy requirements will be about more innovative aspects having a significant impact on elements that characterise the service. In this case, the approach will be descriptive and not as prescriptive, leaving more room for proposals from the market.

The purpose of this subdivision is to crystallise the current market innovation aspects in terms of some aspects (those addressed by the basic requirements) and to stimulate progress towards innovative scenarios in the areas where today’s market is less mature.

(Duration: the drafting of the tender documents needed a few months after the analysis.

Lessons Learned:

Given the complexity of the school food service, a mix of solutions providing for the product, technology, process and organisational innovations is also sought.

- ♦ An aspect of cross innovation was seen into the use ICT in support of sustainability policies within the school catering service: indeed, innovative ICT systems could be proposed – as stated in the proposed requirements – for the management of urban food logistics, for improving energy efficiency in cooking centres and kitchens as well as for educational activities and training aimed at users.
- ♦ As for the strictly technological aspects, no predetermined technological choices have to be made, nor are the solutions envisaged detailed in a prescriptive manner, leaving room for the market to propose the most appropriate solutions as a function of the demand for innovation expressed by the organisation.
- ♦ Since the school catering service is a complex activity made up of a plurality of elements (including quality factors), it is believed that the most economically advantageous offer criterion, which has significant effects on the qualitative aspect of the service, is the most appropriate procedure.
- ♦ As for the strictly technological aspects, **no predetermined technological choices** have to be made, nor are the solutions envisaged detailed in a prescriptive manner, leaving room for the

market to propose the most appropriate solutions as a function of the demand for innovation expressed by the organisation.

- ◆ Since the school catering service is a complex activity made up of a plurality of elements (including quality factors), it is believed that **the most economically advantageous offer criterion**, which has significant effects on the qualitative aspect of the service, is the most appropriate procedure.

PROBIS

Actions:

- ◆ The PPI of Aler Bergamo was explicitly addressed to the following KPIs:
 - ◆ 1. to reduce the consumption of fossil-derived fuel through a set of interventions on the building envelopes and the Space Heating (SH) and sanitary hot water (SHW) plants;
 - ◆ 2. to provide easy regulation, metering, and billing of the SH and SHW consumption.
 - ◆ 3. to keep quantity and cost of maintenance on the heating system and windows below the historical one on similar buildings.
- ◆ A set of additional challenging requirements were defined to increase of the internal thermal comfort and the air quality as well as to have better conditions for tenants. Further objectives considered for the selection of the envisaged solutions were: low environmental impact, minimum time interference and disturbance to tenants, user-friendly solutions, integration with all existing and future ICT appliances, tenants should stay at their homes during renovation, considerably simple and short time of installation with no disruption for tenants.
- ◆ Modus operandi in tendering managed by the PROBIS procurers in the previous years were based on the “lower price” approach. The shifting towards a lower “total” cost of ownership based on a performances evaluation (concerning the Aler Bergamo case, the weight given to the technical offer (75%) versus the economic one (15%)), where the participants are pushed to introduce innovation in technology and process, obliged the procurers to move out from the ordinary and consolidated procedures frame.
- ◆ A proper system of assessing the performance of a contractor with value engineering has been required, not only to reduce the risk of failure but also to set the conditions to deliver better results than the standard. The technical evaluation was accomplished in 1 week, by an internal evaluation commission made by technicians belonging

to different ALER (Public Housing Companies) of the Lombardy Region.

- ◆ Qualification of the received offers and challenges undertaken by companies were also performed. Considering that the participants invested much more resources than the ones usually requested by the ordinary tenders (nearly all the participants had to require the support of external experts in energy efficiency) and the fact that the tender itself was far from the ones they ever met, there was a relevant risk that no one participates. However, several offers were submitted.

Lessons Learned:

- ◆ Effective and strong competition was ensured by the fact that the need was shared by multiple potential buyers/end-users. This type of intervention ensured economies of scale that is key to maximize the potential of innovation procurement.
- ◆ Qualification of the received offers and challenges undertaken by companies were also performed. Considering that the participants had to invest much more resources than the ones usually requested by the ordinary tenders (nearly all the participants had to require the support of external experts in energy efficiency) and the fact that the tender itself was far from the ones they ever met, there was a relevant risk that no one participates. However, 10 offers were submitted. In comparison, the average number of participants to tenders for similar retrofit works is about 80. Mostly qualified contractors likely responded to the tender, as these might be assumed to be the ones most interested in competing in future performances and not on the rebate.
- ◆ The proposals contained different methods and solutions to achieve the desired functionality and produce savings compared to those in the initial executive plan of the procurer at the start of the procurement.
- ◆ Significantly reduced rebate dimension (average 8%) and no need to ask an explanation, due to an excess of rebate on the whole or a single part of an offer, thanks to the weight given to the technical offer (75%) versus the economic one (15%).
- ◆ No participant has appealed against the verdict of the competition commission. Awarding by evaluation of stated performances is a much more critical method than the maximum rebate one.
- ◆ In comparison, 10% of average participants to tenders for similar, but traditional, retrofit works. It has been demonstrated that mostly qualified contractors responded to the tender, as these might be assumed to be the ones most interested in competing in future performances and not on the rebate. Additionally, non-traditional suppliers participated and presented offers.

- ◆ The proposals contained different methods and solutions to achieve the desired functionality and produce savings compared to those in the initial executive plan of the procurer at the start of the procurement. The buyers achieve the key results of comparing different solutions, objectively comparable, based on a clear KPIs and awarding systems.
- ◆ Involvement of specialized architects and professionals with significant experience in sustainable building design, both internally if the intention is to create internal strong competences or on a competitive base in case the design of the works will also be tendered to be sure about the procurement viability and reachability of the minimum targets.
- ◆ If authorities are looking for innovation related to the performance of a specific technology or category of technologies, it is suggested they set a tender regarding this technology only (or even a PCP for radical innovation).
- ◆ Whenever possible, to assure a minimum quality of the intervention and avoid the risk of disputes on its real costs that could be brought by the participants or the awarded contractor, it is quite useful to invest in developing, until the executive stage, a "baseline project". Therefore, each cost will be defined and a "reference minimum quality" for each kind of works and type technology will be detailed, to secure the framework of the performance that will drive the awarding of the tender under the "Most economically advantageous (MEAT)" criteria.

PHASE 4 – EXECUTION - DEPLOYMENT AND WIDE DIFFUSION

HAPPI

Actions:

- ♦ The project partners created a special document, explaining the call-off procedure for each country, as the execution phase differed slightly from one country to another. This document was sent both to the supplier and to all contracting authorities which were interested in calling off.
- ♦ The contract management was conducted by each CPB, separately; nevertheless, there is an obligation to report the call-off results to the lead buyer, which centralises the data.
- ♦ to promote the call-off from the framework agreement awarded. The project partners organised information days for the hospitals and health care institutions to share with them the most important information on the products awarded.
- ♦ End-users. physician, healthcare assistant, hospital staff and citizen

[Duration: the execution phase of the framework agreement was of 4 years by the award of lots (March 2015)]

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ The relevance of monitoring activity on the result of the innovative solution identified
- ♦ The relevance of dissemination to widespread benefit identified through the Project
- ♦ Exchanging good practice with the participating CPBs as well as learning about new procurement practices in the other Member States and cooperate in an international and multidisciplinary team.
- ♦ One of the achievements resulting from the cooperation of CPBs within the HAPPI project was the creation of a procurement organisation called EHPPA (European Health Public Procurement Alliance - <http://www.ehppa.com/>), an alliance of non-profit Group Procurement Organisations, which promotes cross-border cooperation between healthcare institutions when purchasing goods and services, especially in the field of innovation (during the As EHPPA was included on the list of contracting authorities purchasing on behalf of their members, it could provide access to the framework agreement to a multitude of other healthcare organisations in Europe, ensuring that the innovative products are bought on a larger scale).

INNOCAT

Actions:

Compliance control

Knowing the efficacy of compliance control as a stimulus for the actual adoption by the market of the eco-innovations proposed, future tender specifications will provide for monitoring methods similar to those developed within the framework of the INNOCAT project, which, among other things, specified checks on the proper implementation of eco-sustainability aspects.

Control activities will encompass the documentation (e.g., certifications, documented data, material safety data sheets, etc.) as well as on-the-spot verifications.

As a rule, such activities are performed by an independent organisation selected by the City of Turin.

Personnel training

As determined by monitoring current service activities and market conditions, the all-out adoption of eco-sustainability measures calls for active participation of all the players concerned, and especially the people who prepare the meals and deliver the service. The future specifications may, therefore, provide for training activities concerning specific management aspects to strengthen product and process choices and consistently accompany the process of change.

User education and content dissemination

Similarly, an effective process of change towards eco-sustainability goals must necessarily rely on the active participation of service users and – in terms of consequences – the school community as a whole. Accordingly, during the period of validity of the new tender specifications, the City will promote educational initiatives –be carried out to the extent feasible by making use of innovative instruments and modalities – on the food, environmental and social sustainability aspects associated with the school

canteen service². To strengthen this aspect, and for awareness-raising purposes, these guidelines promote – mostly through noteworthy requirements – user training activities to be organised by the future contractors in collaboration with the City of Turin.

The Municipality of Turin included the analysis and evidences in a set of specifications and award criteria in an Official Guideline for the eco-innovative procurement of all schools catering services in Turin. These guidelines have been adopted as an official political act before the end of the project and have been to design the school catering call for tender which was issued in 2018. Due to the critical situation of Italian procurement in this field (with a high rate of appeals to court), the procurement strategy was slightly revised and most of sustainability criteria developed have been directly inserted as an obligation into technical specifications (percentage of organic; use of traditional agri-food products, training for students, etc.).

Duration: The service contract which was Monitored and used as baseline during the project runned from 1 September 2013 until 31 August 2016; it was then prolonged according to contract provisions.

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Creating the baseline and measuring of the climatic impact of the school catering service, to design the procurement
- ♦ Control on the correct execution of the innovations involving Chemical Laboratory, which monitored the activities of the companies entrusted with the catering service in connection with the environmental innovations already in force based on the procurement specifications for the school canteen service. The monitoring activities performed during the first year of the new procurement contract (school year 2013/14) revealed that the companies substantially adhered to the new rules, though some of the innovative aspects – on account of their special complexity – could not be fully implemented until the following school year.
- ♦ Among the “strengths” identified, we should mention compliance in terms of fruit seasonality and origin of the products, from Piedmont and organic or integrated pest management farming. On the other hand, some aspects need improving (e.g., monitoring of vehicles).
- ♦ Generally, the tool for the control of the correct execution has been a good instrument to support the innovation policies by stimulating the awarding companies to put in practise efficiently the requirements and create a new market for these solutions.

² For information on current and future educational/training activities, see:

PROBIS

Actions:

The awarded competitor included a mechanical ventilation system, with heat recovery, per each dwelling. A test of the system on two empty dwellings was executed at the start of the works.

The performance-based procurement enforced the innovation-driven demand-side modus operandi to be extended for the

Lessons Learned:

- ♦ Due to the nature of a PPI, it must manage different types of risk. Although the technological uncertainties are low in a PPI (solutions closer to market), there are other risks in PPIs: risks of deployment failure (damages to operational installations, end-users), large scale production or delivery hick-ups, large scale project financing complexities, etc. As the potential damages of a PPI failure are relevant (having real impacts on life operations), care must be exercised in verifying that the innovative solution effectively satisfies public procurers' need and is viable.
- ♦ This entails careful verification of market readiness to deliver solutions compliant with the requirements before awarding contracts but also a value engineering approach that vendors need to keep on doing product improvement and/or cost reduction to ensure that the outcomes of the PPI fit the real-life reality/environment in which products need to be deployed and improve the performances.
- ♦ The used approach ensured that contractors keep on fulfilling their obligation to deliver the best possible value for money for the public procurer after the contract has been signed. All procurements face a complex mix of technologies and building processes, which is provided by many manufacturers and service companies. The building construction and refurbishment face some different kinds of peculiarities:
 - a. This kind of interventions, do not have a testing phase with the possibility to evaluate, modify and, in case, abandon the project.
 - b. The most appropriate solution (or solutions) is not always coincident with the simple sum of the best innovative products and technologies available on the market. Moreover, tailoring the requirements only on them, it could limit the competition and the development of other appropriate cost-effective solutions;
 - c. On the other side, they leave space for innovation in the system design and installations, in the effort to improve general performances of the refurbishments, including the user's discomforts.

- ◆ Procurement in the constructions sector concerns complex systems, where every component could influence the overall performance. For the housing companies and the Public Administrations involved in the Probis Project, the cost related performances (Energy saving and Maintenance costs) are non the main focus or, their achievement has not to affect one of the other kinds of performances. 6 Site Min. technologies installation time Minimum annoyance for the users Indoor hygro-thermal comfort Indoor air quality Indoor lighting quality and control Reduced maintenance works Reduced maintenance costs ENERGY SAVING Borlange 50% Bergamo 25-30% Torino 15-20%
- ◆ Attention should be assigned to the potential risks of the project. Risks may take several forms, such as market risks (a type of collaboration, procurement not being large enough, timing, and location), legal risks (changes in policies for buildings), and organizational risks (risk aversion from housing companies). The potential risks, during all of the steps in the procurement process, should be taken under consideration during the whole project. If

these risks may be foreseen and proactive rather than reactive measures can be undertaken, the procurement process may be significantly enhanced. Furthermore, a flexible timetable is essential since the procurement process is found to be highly non-linear.

- ◆ In an existing building, innovation is not necessarily defined by a top performance technology or set of technologies, but rather the possibilities to easily concern a high level of flexibility that allows innovation to adapt to the existing situation to get the best overall results compared with the real situation of the building and its framework.
- ◆ When dealing with the implementation of retrofit work on a building or with the construction of a new building, the more specific technology (or set of technologies) drives the evaluation method, the less quality can be guaranteed to the whole intervention and the reverse.

5. OVERVIEW ACTIONS IMPLEMENTED BY PPI PROJECTS

Find, below, where you can find more information and detailed activities' planning on the different PPI phases.

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Needs Analysis:

- ◆ Surveys
- ◆ Workshops/ WIBGI Workshops
- ◆ Desktop Research

=> Target audiences: end-users

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Market analysis

- ◆ Surveys to assess the SoA
- ◆ Participation in events
- ◆ PIN (Prior Information Notice)
- ◆ Baseline definition
- ◆ Desk analysis and assessment of the innovation gap, based on TRL

=> Target audiences: suppliers

PHASE 0 – PREPARATION PHASE | Tender Documentation, Launch and Assessment:

- ◆ Publication of ITT / Call

PHASE 3 – EXECUTION – DEPLOYMENT WIDE DIFFUSION

- ◆ Monitoring of contractors' progress
- ◆ Regular meetings with suppliers
- ◆ Participation in events to disseminate pilot solutions
- ◆ The organisation of training events
- ◆ Collection of feedback from suppliers (surveys) NA

6. DISCOVER OTHER PROJECTS

We gathered a list of completed PCP and PPI projects funded by EU, in the area of ICT, to support your further exploration around the experiences lived by other projects.

TYPE	NAME	START DATE	END DATE	DOMAIN	NO. PARTNERS	NO. PROCURERS	NAME OF PROCURERS	LINK TO CORDIS
PCP	CHARM	Sept 2012	Aug 2017	TRANSPORT	5	3	Rijkswaterstaat (NL), Highways Agency (UK). Other traffic management authorities associated to the procurement: Department of Mobility of Works (BE)	URL
PCP	DECIPHER	Feb 2012	Mar 2017	HEALTH / ELDERLY CARE	14	3	Fundation TicSalut (ES), ESTAV Centro (IT), TRUSTECH – Central Manchester Foundation Trust (UK)	URL
PCP	HNSciCloud	Jan 2016	Dec 2018	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	12	10	European Organization for Nuclear Research CERN (CH), National Institute for Nuclear Physics INFN (IT), German Electron-Synchrotron DESY (DE), National Center for Scientific Research CNRS (FR), Karlsruhe Institute for Technology KIT (DE), SURFsara (NL), Science and Technology Facilities Council STFC (UK), European Molecular Biology Laboratory EMBL-EBI (DE), Institute for High Energy Physics IFAE (ES), European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF)	URL
PCP	IMAILE	Feb 2014	Jan 2018	EDUCATION	13	4	Halmstad municipality (SE), Ministry of Finance of Saxony Anhalt (DE), City council of Viladecans (ES), Municipality of Konnevsj (FI)	URL
PCP	NYMPHA-MD	Jan 2014	Sept 2017	HEALTH / ELDERLY CARE	5	3	Autonomous Province of Trento (IT), Mental Health Services Capital Region Copenhagen (DK), CSPT – University Hospital (ES)	URL
PCP	PRACE-3IP	Jul 2012	Dec 2017	ENERGY	48	5	CINECA (IT), Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH (DE), Genci (FR), EPCC (UK), CSC (FI)	URL
PCP	PREFORMA	Jan 2014	Dec 2017	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	15	9	National Archives-Riksarkivet (SE), Sound and Image-Beelden Geluid (NL), Royal Institute for art Patrimonium-KIK (BE), Greek Film Center (GR), Local Government Management Agency – LGMA (IE), Foundation Prussian Cultural Heritage (DE), Town Hall Girona (ES), Ministry of Culture–EVKM (EE), National Library – Kungliga Biblioteket (SE)	URL
PCP	SELECT for Cities	Dec 2015	Nov 2019	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	7	3	cities of Antwerp, Copenhagen and Helsinki	URL
PCP	SILVER	Jan 2012	Aug 2016	HEALTH / ELDERLY CARE	13	7	The public procurers in the SILVER consortium are: City of Eindhoven, City of Odense, City of Oulu, City of Stockport,	URL

							City of Vantaa, City of Västerås and Region of Southern Denmark.
PCP	SMART@FIRE	Nov 2012	Mar 2017	SAFETY	13	5	Federal Home Affairs Ministry (BE), SDIS Fire Department Bouches-du-Rhone (FR). Other procurers associated to the procurement: Fire Department city Dortmund (DE), Greater Manchester Fire and Rescue Authority (UK), National Disaster Response Agency (NL) URL
PCP	THALEA	Nov 2013	Oct 2016	HEALTH / ELDERLY CARE	8	5	University Hospital RWTH Aachen (Germany), Oulu University Hospital (Finland), Parc Tauli Sabadell University Hospital (Spain), Maastricht University Medical Center (The Netherlands) and East Limburg Hospital (Belgium). URL
PCP	V-Con	Oct 2012	Mar 2017	TRANSPORT	4	3	Rijkswaterstaat (NL), Trafficverket (SE) Other procurers associated to the procurement: Centre Scientifique et Technique du batiment (FR) URL
PPI	STOP AND GO	Apr 2014	Mar 2018	HEALTH / ELDERLY CARE	19	7	ASP Catanzaro (IT), ASL Roma D (IT), SO.RE.SA (IT), Eastern Cheshire CCG (UK), City of Liverpool (UK), Santa Creu I Sant Pau hospital (ES), City of Helmond (NL) URL

7. SOURCES

IMAILE

Streamlined PCP Process. [LINK](#)
Publishable Summary. [LINK](#)
White Paper on Open Innovation. [LINK](#)

Helix Nebula

D2.1. Report on the Open Market Consultation and the Results. [LINK](#)
D2.2. Tender Material Publication. [LINK](#)
D3.2. Summary report of the design stage and lessons learned. [LINK](#)
D5.2. Summary report of the pilot stage and lessons learned. [LINK](#)
D6.1. Best Practices Report. [LINK](#)
Booklet. Bridging cloud computing innovation & Open Science. [LINK](#)

SILVER

D5.1. Learning and recommendations report – Post competition. [LINK](#)
D5.2. Learning and recommendations report – Post phase 1. [LINK](#)
D5.3. Learning and recommendations report – Post phase 2. [LINK](#)
D5.4. Learning and recommendations report – Post phase 3. [LINK](#)
D5.5. Learning and recommendations report – Overall. [LINK](#)
D5.6. Consolidated Generic Pre-Commercial Procurement Process. [LINK](#)
SILVER Market Consultation. [LINK](#)

PRACE-3IP

D2.1.1. Methodology and Terms of Reference of the PCP Pilot. [LINK](#)
D8.1.1. Technical Specifications for the PCP and for Phase 1. [LINK](#)
D2.1.2. First Report on the joint PCP Pilot (Phase I). [LINK](#)
D2.1.4. Third Report on the joint PCP Pilot (Phase 3). [LINK](#)
D8.1.2. Report on the Technical Specification and Evaluation Criteria for Phase 2. [LINK](#)
D8.1.3. Report on the Technical Specification and Evaluation Criteria for PRACE-PCP Phase 3. [LINK](#)
Fact Sheet – PRACE Pre-Commercial Procurement. [LINK](#)
D5.2. PRACE Integrated HPC Access Programme for SMEs [SHAPE]. [LINK](#)

HAPPI

PPI2INNOVATE TOOL – GUIDA AL PPI NEL SETTORE “SMART – HEALTH”. [LINK](#)
G.M Racca, C.R Yukins Joint Public Procurement and Innovation: Lessons Across Borders, 2020. [LINK](#)
Happi. [LINK](#)

INNOCAT

Resources of the CITY GROUP SEMINAR - Procura+ Barcelona 12.11.2015.
Internal Guidelines on how to reduce the ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF SCHOOL CANTEEN SERVICES, Comune di Torino.
Innocat. [LINK](#)

PROBIS

D.7f PPI Case studies, Lessons learned and recommendations report

